

**STRENGTH DISTRIBUTION OF MONOFILAMENTS
USED FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITES**

H. Fukuda*, T. Miyazawa** and H. Tomatsu**
Department of Materials Science and Technology
Science University of Tokyo
2641 Yamazaki, Noda, Chiba 278, Japan
* Associate Professor, ** Graduate Student

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with a micromechanics of advanced composites. The characteristics of individual fibers, matrix, and fiber/matrix interface are the most important factors for evaluating fiber-reinforced composite materials from a micromechanical view point. Among them, the strength distribution of each fiber is the key factor because most of applied load is carried by fibers.

To this purpose, we first developed a testing device with which the load-elongation curve of a monofilament can be obtained. Filament diameter was measured by the aid of laser diffraction. Using these devices, we have tensile tested several kinds of monofilaments and accumulated data.

Next, tensile test of unidirectional composites has been conducted and the strength was compared with several existing theories.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials are nowadays used in various fields including aerospace, transportation, civil engineering, sports and so on. There are many kinds of fibers as well as matrices with which composite materials are fabricated. The number of combination is not a few. Therefore, it is desirable to know the macroscopic properties of composites from the properties of constituent materials. If it becomes possible, material design will become more effective.

In the present paper, a tensile test of monofilament is first done and data are accumulated. Fiber/matrix interfacial property is next evaluated. Using these basic data, analytical work and computer simulation are carried out to evaluate the strength of a unidirectional composite and results are compared with experimental data.

2. MONOFILAMENT TEST

2.1 Monofilament Test Device

Figure 1 shows a monofilament test device which was designed and machined by

Fig.1 Monofilament test device

ourselves. By rotating the screw, the crosshead moves to right and tensile load is applied to the monofilament. The tensile load can be measured by a strain gage which is attached on the leaf-spring. This idea of using leaf-spring was borrowed from Ref.[1]. The elongation of the monofilament can also be calculated from the movement of the crosshead and the deflection of the leaf spring.

2.2 Measurement of Diameter

It is necessary to measure the diameter of each monofilament in order to calculate the strength of each fiber. Although a scanning electron microscopy would be a good candidate to measure precisely the diameter, it is not

Fig.2 Schematic view of test apparatus to measure filament diameter

suitable to measure one by one the diameter of monofilament which is to be tensile tested. Then as an alternative, we used a laser diffraction method.

Figure 2 is the test apparatus to measure the diameter by means of laser diffraction. By measuring the distance between dark spots of the diffraction pattern, the filament diameter can be calculated as

$$d = \frac{2L\lambda}{l} \quad (1)$$

where d is the filament diameter, L is the distance between the specimen and the screen, λ is the wave length of laser light (He-Ne laser, $\lambda=632.8$ nm), and l is the distance between dark spots.

However, this laser diffraction method may include some errors. Then the average value calculated by eq.(1) was compared with the diameter measured with SEM. Assuming the SEM value is correct, eq.(1) was modified by multiplying a factor.

Fig.3 Cumulative distribution of the strength of Kevlar 49 monofilaments (gage length = 25 mm)

2.3 Results and Discussion for Monofilament Test

Carbon (Torayca T300), glass (E-glass), aramid (Kevlar 49) and alumina (Sumitomo SX-11) monofilaments were tensile tested. All tests were carried out at the gage length of 25mm, although the gage length was varied in the preliminary study. Test data were analyzed by a two-parameter Weibull distribution where the number of specimens was 50-60. Figure 3 is an example of the cumulative distribution of the strength of monofilaments. As is shown in this Figure, tensile strength obeyed pretty well the Weibull distribution. Table 1 summarizes the Weibull parameters for four kinds of fibers, where m and α are, respectively, the shape parameter and the scale parameter.

3. DRY BUNDLE TEST

3.1 Results

Dry bundle test was carried out next where dry bundle means mere fiber bundle with no matrix. Carbon bundle (3000 monofilaments) and alumina bundle (1000

Fig.4 Load-elongation curves of bundles,
 (a) T300 bundle, (b) alumina bundle

Table 1 Monofilament Properties

	Tensile Strength (GPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Weibull Parameters		Ineffective Length (mm)
			m	α (GPa)	
T300	2.91	232	5.1	3.17	0.30
E-glass	2.24	75.4	5.4	2.43	-
Kevlar49	2.24	128	11.3	3.65	-
SX-11	2.28	216	4.9	2.49	0.45

monofilaments) were evaluated where the gage length was 200mm. Each bundle was mounted on an Instron-type testing machine and tensile load was applied. Figure 4 shows some examples of the load-elongation curves where the curves of "DRY" is of the present concern.

3.2 Comparison with Coleman's Theory

The bundle strength was evaluated by Coleman's theory. The strength distribution of monofilaments is assumed to obey Weibull distribution. According to Coleman[3], the bundle strength is

$$\frac{F_b}{F_{mono}} = \left(\frac{1}{m}\right)^{1/m} \frac{1}{\Gamma(1+1/m)} \quad (2)$$

where F_b is the bundle strength, F_{mono} is the monofilament strength

Table 2 Dry bundle strength

	Monofilament F _{mono} (GPa)	Dry Bundle σ _b (GPa)	σ _b / F _{mono}		Wet Bundle Exp. (GPa)
			Exp.	Theory	
T300	1.94	1.29	0.662	0.651	2.88
SX-11	1.50	1.07	0.720	0.644	1.93

extrapolated from the measured value (25mm length) to 200mm, m is the shape parameter, and Γ is the gamma function.

Table 2 shows both experimental and theoretical values. Extrapolation was done under the assumption of Weibull distribution. For carbon bundle, the value of eq.(2) is 0.651 whereas the experimental value is 0.662. For alumina bundle, these are 0.644 and 0.720. Thus it may be concluded that the strength of dry bundle can be estimated quite well from Coleman's theory.

4. STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE

4.1 Fiber/Matrix Interaction

Prior to the tensile test of unidirectional composites, fiber/matrix interaction was checked which becomes necessary for the prediction of the strength of unidirectional composites.

A monofilament was embedded in an epoxy matrix and tensile load was applied until the filament no longer broke in the matrix. A so-called ineffective length (δ) was defined here as the average length of the filament fragment, which is listed in Table 1.

4.2 Experimental Results for Unidirectional Composites

Both resin impregnated carbon and alumina bundle were tested here. Epoxy resin (Epicote 828) with amine hardner (S-cure 661) was used for matrix. The cure schedule was 17 hours at 65 C followed by 5 hours at 140 C. Test results are shown in Fig.4 with the notation of "WET."

4.3 Comparison with Theoretical Model

The above experimental values were compared with some theoretical models. Models discussed here are (1)Rosen model[4], (2) Zweben model[5] and (3) modified Zweben model.

4.3.1 Rosen Model

According to Rosen[4], the strength of a unidirectional composite is

$$\frac{F_b}{F_{mono}} = \left(\frac{n}{me} \right)^{1/m} \frac{1}{\Gamma(1+1/m)} \quad (3)$$

where n is the number of links of a filament. In the Rosen model, a so-called stress concentration factor due to fiber breakage is not taken into account.

Fig.5 Monte Carlo simulation of the strength of unidirectional composites (Zweben)

4.3.2 Zweben Model

In the Zweben model[5], the stress concentration is taken into consideration. However, it becomes difficult to calculate the strength analytically. Then a Monte Carlo simulation was carried out to evaluate the Zweben model. Hedgepeth's two dimensional analysis on the stress concentration factor[6] was adopted here. The procedure of the simulation is similar to Ref.[7], although the normal distribution used in Ref.[7] was replaced with the Weibull distribution. Random numbers, η , which obey Weibull distribution can be generated from uniform random numbers, ξ , by using the following conversion:

$$\eta = \alpha \{-\log(1-\xi)\}^{1/m} \quad (4)$$

Only carbon/epoxy unidirectional composites were simulated. Since the measured ineffective length is 0.3mm for carbon/epoxy (see Table 1), the number of links of each monofilament of 200 mm length becomes 667 (200mm/0.3mm). The combination of this number and 3000 filaments are too large for the simulation. Then only 16 cases (combination of number of links = 5, 10, 20, 40 and number of fibers = 5, 10, 20, 40) were simulated.

Open marks of Fig.5 is the average of 100 iterations. Using these simulated data, the strength at the gage length of 200 mm was extrapolated; solid marks in the Figure are the results. Extrapolation was also conducted against the number of filaments and the solid diamond mark is the final result which corresponds 3000 filament rod of 200 mm length.

4.3.3 Modified Zweben Model

In both Rosen and Zweben model, final fracture was assumed to take place within an ineffective length, δ . In the actual failure, however, fiber pull-out or fiber/matrix debonding are commonly observed. Then Zweben model was modified here so that the fiber/matrix debonding can be taken into account[8], although the introduction of the fiber/matrix debonding is rather qualitative. The assumption used here is that if r successive fibers (links) are broken within the same ineffective length, this "crack" can be combined with another

crack which is within the longitudinal distance of $r\delta$.

The procedure of simulation is the same as the case of Zweben model. Figure 6 is an example of the failure pattern of Zweben model and modified Zweben model. Each row represents each monofilament. The numeral 0 is an unbroken link and successive numbers show the order of the link failure. In this modified Zweben model, fiber/matrix debonding is realised, although it is qualitative.

Figure 7 is the final result. According to the experimental value, Rosen model overestimates the strength and Zweben model underestimates it. These will be reasonable because Rosen model doesn't consider the stress concentration and Zweben model overestimates the stress concentration factor. Concerning the modified Zweben model, it was inferior to Zweben model as far as the strength is concerned. However, the failure pattern is close to the actual failure. Thus, if adequate evaluation of the stress concentration factor is done for three-dimensional model in future, the modified Zweben model may become more reliable.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In the present paper, monofilament test was first done and Weibull parameters were decided. Tensile test of dry bundle was next performed and it was made clear that the strength of dry bundle agrees fairly well with Coleman's theory.

The tensile test of unidirectional composite was carried out next. Experimental data were compared with some theoretical models. It was made clear that Rosen model overestimates the strength whereas Zweben model underestimates it. A modified Zweben model can represent the actual failure pattern, although some subjects are left for future investigation.

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a) Zweben

b) Modified Zweben

Fig.6 Example of failure pattern

Fig.7 Strength of unidirectional composites (T300/Epoxy)

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